

Review Article

Robotics for poultry farming: Challenges and opportunities

Uğur Özentürk^{a,b}, Zhengqi Chen^c, Lorenzo Jamone^c, Elisabetta Versace^{a,*}^a School of Biological and Behavioural Sciences, Department of Biological and Experimental Psychology, Queen Mary University of London, UK^b Ataturk University, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Animal Science, Turkiye^c ARQ (Advanced Robotics at Queen Mary), School of Engineering and Materials Science, Queen Mary University of London, UK

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Animal welfare
Poultry farming
Robotics
Robot-animal interaction
Social interactions

ABSTRACT

Poultry farming plays a pivotal role in addressing human food demand. Robots are emerging as promising tools in poultry farming, with the potential to address sustainability issues while meeting the increasing production needs and demand for animal welfare. This review presents current advancements and limitations in robotics in poultry farming, and outlines future directions of development including robot-animal interactions. We survey the application of robots in different areas, from environmental monitoring to disease control, floor eggs collection and animal welfare. Robots not only demonstrate effective implementation on farms but also hold potential for ethological research on collective and social behaviour, which can in turn drive a better integration in industrial farming, with improved productivity and enhanced animal welfare.

1. Introduction

Poultry farming plays a crucial role in meeting the growing demand for affordable and safe food products (Sarica et al., 2018). Not only poultry production is cost-effective but it offers high-quality proteins too (Ahmad et al., 2022; Attia et al., 2022; de Mesquita Souza Saraiva et al., 2022). Furthermore, poultry farming contributes to economic and social sustainability by creating favourable investment opportunities for producers (Rodić et al., 2011). On the other hand, several challenges are critical for sustainability in modern poultry farming (Gunnarsson et al., 2020; Hafez and Attia, 2020) including animal health and welfare, poultry house management, production, and human-induced issues, such as possible contamination. For economical and practical reasons, the management of poultry farming is transitioning from human labour to smart systems facilitated by machines, including robots (Ren et al., 2020). While the application of smart technologies in poultry farming is expected to enable faster and more effective farm and animal monitoring, leading to better-informed decision-making through the evaluation of extensive data (Sharma and Patil, 2018), it also introduces novel perspectives and challenges (Fernyhough et al., 2020; Hafez and Attia, 2020).

Among the various technological tools, robots are emerging as a prominent solution in poultry farming, serving diverse functions such as phenotyping, monitoring, management, and environmental control (Sahoo et al., 2022). Recently, functional robots have been developed in

poultry farming that can perform specific tasks – such as collecting floor eggs and dead birds, thus saving labour and facilitating the production (Astill et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022; Zhao, 2021). However, research on the impact of robots designed for direct contact with animals on animal health and welfare is limited (Dennis et al., 2020; Parajuli et al., 2020). Additionally, robots have shown potential in studying collective and social behaviour through interaction with animals, with robot-animal interaction becoming a promising research area (Gribovskiy et al., 2018). Such studies are inspired by the rapid social attachment mechanism known as filial imprinting observed in young animals (Bolhuis, 1991; McCabe, 2013; Vallortigara and Versace, 2022; Wang et al., 2024). Robots interacting with animals hold a huge potential in the investigation of social behaviour and ethological research because they enable highly standardized, controlled, replicable and reproducible experimental designs. This innovative approach allows to explore complex social dynamics in various species (Gribovskiy et al., 2018; Krause et al., 2011; Romano et al., 2019).

There is growing interest in robotics for poultry farming. Previous work has explored the potential impact of smart technology in the poultry industry, focusing on robotics, advanced sensors, automation technology, AI (Artificial Intelligence), big data analysis, internet of things, and transportation (Abbas et al., 2022; Park et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022). Robot-animal social interactions and the impact of robots on animal welfare and animal behaviour in poultry had limited coverage. Thus, this review primarily focuses on robots

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: e.versace@qmul.ac.uk (E. Versace).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2024.109411>

Received 22 November 2023; Received in revised form 30 July 2024; Accepted 28 August 2024

Available online 7 September 2024

0168-1699/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

developed for poultry farming, robot-animal interactions, and their applications in social interactions. Moreover, we identify research directions that aim to enhance poultry welfare and healthy behaviour. After discussing the current challenges in poultry farming (section 2), we describe robots currently used in different tasks in poultry farming (section 3) and then assess robot-animal interactions (section 4). The discussion examines the main current limitations of robots in poultry farming and future directions of research.

2. Current challenges in poultry farming

The poultry industry has enhanced production via rapid growth rates in broilers and increased egg productivity in layers (Kleyn and Ciaciarriello, 2021). Despite these advancements in poultry production, there are still various challenges for the sector in its current state and future development, including disease outbreaks, welfare regulations, and environmental factors that affect production practices (Ferryhough et al., 2020; Hafez and Attia, 2020; Mottet and Tempio, 2017; Penz and Bruno, 2011). In this section, we outline the current challenges of poultry farming in four key areas: animal health and welfare, poultry house management, production, and human-induced issues.

2.1. Animal health and welfare

Ensuring animal health is crucial in poultry farms. Poultry diseases pose a significant threat, as some of them have the potential to escalate into pandemics with far-reaching global consequences (Carenzi and Verga, 2009). To mitigate such risks, continuous monitoring of poultry is essential for disease prevention, biosecurity measures, early diagnosis, and timely treatment (Aggrey, 2009; Pearce et al., 2023). Robotic solutions have been developed to detect diseases and monitor mortality in poultry houses (section 3.2). Furthermore, certain robots contribute to animal health by encouraging animal activity (section 3.5).

Upholding animal welfare (Webster, 2005) and “life worth living” (Mellor, 2016) while ensuring sustainable production practices (Yang et al., 2020) is another challenge. To achieve a comprehensive assessment of animal welfare, standardized parameters must be established and accurately monitored (Penz and Bruno, 2011; Wemelsfelder and Mullan, 2014). The evaluation of animal welfare revolves around indicators such as proper nutrition, good health, suitable housing, and appropriate behaviour (Butterworth et al., 2009; Paul et al., 2022). To evaluate animal welfare, it is fundamental to understand the natural behaviour of a poultry species (Abeyesinghe et al., 2021; Ferreira et al., 2020; Nicol, 2020; Putyora et al., 2023), including social behaviour. The robots mentioned in section 4.2 are designed to monitor welfare and support social behaviour by focusing on social interaction among chicks.

2.2. Poultry house management

Among livestock systems, poultry systems are considered environmentally friendly, because produce low greenhouse gas emissions (Leinonen and Kyriazakis, 2016; Vries and de Boer (2010)) and lower water usage (Gerber et al., 2015; Vaarst et al., 2015). However, they still require special attention to their environmental impact, particularly concerning issues such as ammonia release and nitrate leaching. Environmental impacts on poultry farms arise directly from energy use, housing, and manure management. To enhance environmental sustainability, it is crucial to measure and monitor the level of environmental impacts overall. Improving poultry housing and developing new strategies for manure management have the potential to further improve the environmental sustainability of the poultry industry (Costantini et al., 2021; Leinonen and Kyriazakis, 2016; Vaarst et al., 2015).

Maintaining optimum environmental conditions needs proficient and stable poultry house management at every stage of production (Flora et al., 2022). Environmental factors, including temperature, humidity, ventilation, gas concentration, and lighting, profoundly

influence poultry health and performance (ElZanaty, 2014; Sarica et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2016). Robots equipped with various sensors can effectively monitor the climatic environmental conditions in the poultry house (see section 3.1).

Another vital aspect is litter management. Contaminants, such as feed residues and faeces, can lead to the proliferation of bacteria in the litter. Accumulation of waste can result in increased ammonia gas levels in the poultry house due to microbial decomposition (Sakamoto et al., 2020). High humidity in the litter also poses a significant problem for flock health and welfare (Sakamoto et al., 2020). Therefore, the litter must be regularly monitored and effectively managed throughout the production cycle (Sakamoto et al., 2020). We discuss robotic solutions for litter management in Section 3.4.

2.3. Production

Challenges in poultry production encompass ensuring food safety while maintaining low production costs. Expenses related to feed, maintenance, and equipment constitute the fundamental costs, but production losses also significantly impact farming operations (Hafez and Attia, 2020). Identifying low-yielding hens in egg production and closely monitoring their egg-laying behaviour can aid in cost reduction (Aral et al., 2017; Dogan et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022).

Free range systems in poultry farming are a method of where hens are provided access to outdoor areas for at least part of the day (Miao et al., 2005; Petek and Çavuşoğlu, 2021). These systems give hens to areas with nests, perches and litter, allowing them greater mobility and opportunities for natural behaviour (Hartcher and Jones, 2017). However, it's important to note that floor egg problems can arise in these systems, leading to reduced production (Oliveira et al., 2019). Collecting eggs from the floor becomes a daily task, which increases labour costs. Additionally, eggs left on the floor can be broken or eaten by birds. Moreover, if the eggs are not collected promptly, they may mix with the litter and manure, elevating the risk of contamination and adversely affecting food quality and safety (Li et al., 2020a; Chai, 2022). Robotics solutions have the potential to streamline egg collection, minimize production losses, and enhance food safety standards in poultry farming, as discussed in Section 3.3.

2.4. Human-induced issues

The general duties of breeders in the poultry industry encompass daily care of the animals, health, and welfare control, and monitoring of the poultry house. Additionally, breeders are responsible for the daily egg collection and dispatch in laying hen breeding. However, with the increase in herd size and the adoption of different breeding systems, the observation and management of the herd have become more challenging (Vroegindewij et al., 2018). Manual observations are labour-intensive, time-consuming, costly, and prone to subjective information (Parajuli et al., 2020). Therefore, the implementation of automatic monitoring equipment and effective use of technology is imperative to achieve efficient monitoring and informed decision-making (Buijs et al., 2018; Buijs et al., 2020; George, 2024; Vroegindewij et al., 2018).

Furthermore, breeders' increased activities within the poultry house may cause stress in the animals and lead to cross-contamination by carrying disease factors between the birds. Such situations pose risks to occupational health and safety (George, 2024; Ren et al., 2020). The robots discussed in Section 3 offer potential solutions to overcome human-induced problems in poultry houses with their functionalities. Additionally, the comparison between robot-animal interaction and human-animal interaction is presented in section 4.1, shedding light on the potential benefits of using robots to minimize stress and improve animal welfare in poultry farming operations.

Table 1
Robots used in poultry farming.

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
Poultry House Management (sec. 2.2)	Environmental monitoring (sec. 3.1) Cited rob. res:5	Mobility Communication Measurement – Temperature – Humidity – Air speed – CO ₂ – NH ₃ – Noise level – Light Obtain information – Collecting data – Message or email – Alarm	Scout	Scout, 2023	Cage-free farm	
			Poultry Patrol	Poultry Patrol, 2019	Cage-free farm	
			Octopus XO	Octopus XO, 2021	Cage-free farm	
			Robot (Liu et al., 2016) RoboChick	Liu et al., 2016 Demmers et al., 2019	Laying hens Cage-free farm	
Animal Health and Welfare (sec. 2.1)	Disease control (sec. 3.2) Cited rob. res:12	Detecting sick birds Detecting dead birds – Temperature – Movement Removal dead birds – Vision system – Flexibility – Mobility	Robot (Li, 2016)	Li, 2016	Laying hens- cage system	
			Poultry Patrol	Poultry Patrol, 2019	Cage-free farm	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
			Scout	Scout, 2023	Cage-free farm	
			BroilerRemoval robot	Liu et al., 2021	Cage-free farm	
			BroilerRemoval robot	Li et al., 2022	Broiler	
		Chicken Nannies		Chicken Nannies, 2017	Laying hens- cage system	
		Dead Broiler Inspection Platform		Hao et al., 2022	Broiler	
		Dead Chicken Recognition Robot		Lai et al., 2023	Cage system	
		Multi-layer Robot		Lei et al., 2022	Broiler	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
			Versatile Poultry Robot	Jan et al., 2022	Cage-free farm	
			Sensyn Robotics	Sensyn Robotics, Inc. 2023	Laying hens- cage system	
Production (sec. 2.3)	Collecting floor eggs (sec. 3.3) Cited rob. res:12	Detect and collect floor eggs Localisation Navigation Path planning Avoiding obstacles Interacting animal Sorting – Weight – SizeStore	Birds Eye Robotics PoultryBot	Birds Eye Robotics, 2023 Vroegindweij et al., 2014a; 2014b; 2014c; 2016; 2018	Cage-free farm Cage-free farm, Laying hens	
			Smart Poultry Robot	Chang et al., 2020	Cage-free farm, Laying hens	
			GohBot	Joffe and Usher, 2017; Usher et al., 2017	Cage-free farm, Laying hens	
			Robotic arm	Li et al., 2020a; 2021	Laying hens	
			Versatile Poultry Robot	Jan et al., 2022	Cage-free farm	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
			Egg Picking Robot	Wang et al., 2019	Cage-free farm	
Poultry House Management (sec. 2.2)	Aeration of the litter and disinfection (sec. 3.4) Cited rob. res:12	Localization Mobility Scraping Navigation Sanitation- Spraying	Sputnic Nav	Tibot, 2021	Cage-free farm	
			Octopus XO	Octopus XO, 2021	Cage-free farm	
			Disinfection Robot	Feng and Wang, 2020; Feng et al., 2021	Cage-free farm	
			Poultry Patrol	Poultry Patrol, 2019	Cage-free farm	
			Versatile Poultry Robot	Jan et al., 2022	Cage-free farm	
			Mobile Robot + Iot	Kunz Cechinel et al., 2024	Cage-free farm	
			Birds Eye Robotics	Birds Eye Robotics, 2023	Cage-free farm	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
			Firstlit Automatic Bedding Robot	FirstPellets, 2023	Cage-free farm	
			Sentinel Automatic Bedding Robot	Inateco by Dussau, 2023	Cage-free farm	
			PoultryMate Automatic Bedding Robot	Poultry Matic Kft., 2023	Cage-free farm	
Animal Health and Welfare (sec. 2.1)	Encouraging Bird Activity (sec.3.5) Cited rob. res:8	Trigger the bird's movement Autonomous mobility Avoiding obstacle	Spoutnic Nav	Tibot, 2021	Cage-free farm	
			T-Moov	T-Moov, 2022	Cage-free farm	
			Scout	Scout, 2023	Cage-free farm	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of Cited Robotic Researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target farm animal	Robots
			Octopus XO	Octopus XO, 2021	Cage-free farm	
			Ground robot	Li et al., 2022b	Cage-free farm	
			AviSense Robot	Marin et al., 2024	Cage-free farm	
			Robotic Vehicle	Yang et al., 2020	Cage-free farm	
			RoboChick	Demmers et al., 2019	Cage-free farm	

et al., 2019) as a chicken house inspection robot. It was equipped with temperature and humidity sensors, carbon dioxide sensors, and acoustic wind speed sensors, enabling it to monitor the environmental conditions of the chicken house.

Many of the robots designed to provide environmental monitoring and information in poultry have been developed by commercial companies. Often, these companies do not disclose their data, which poses a limitation to the transparency and reproducibility of their findings. Moreover, scientific research and accessible published resources on these poultry robots remain limited. To assess the operational success and effectiveness of these robotic systems, it is crucial to conduct experimental research and share the results. The publication of research findings would facilitate knowledge dissemination and enable fellow researchers and industry professionals to make informed decisions. Robotic systems that have undergone experimental testing and demonstrate the ability to support the traceability of poultry houses are poised to find broader applications in the industry in the future. Further research and dissemination can expand the use of these technologies in poultry farming.

3.2. Disease control

Pathogenic infections are among the most critical challenges in poultry farming, as they can spread rapidly within the poultry house (section 2.1). Researchers have focused on developing robotic systems to quickly identify sick animals and remove dead birds from the herd (Li, 2016). Equipping robots with sensors for early warning systems allows the monitoring of disease and food safety-related pathogens in birds (Abbas et al., 2022; Park et al., 2022).

Nanny robots (Charoen Pokphand Group) are designed to monitor the body temperature and movements of animals in conventional 3-layer cage systems using thermal cameras. The robot can detect sick and dead chickens by identifying birds with abnormal temperature values and inactivity (Chicken Nannies, 2017). Li (2016) designed a robot to identify sick and dead birds in cages. The robot warns the

animals by hitting the cage and detects the movements of the birds using image processing methods. However, the manual operation and hitting action may cause increased stress in birds. Liu et al. (2021) designed a robot with two modes to remove dead chickens from the poultry house. One mode allows for remote control, while the other is autonomous, and the system can work without human intervention. The robotic system includes arms, a conveyor belt, a storage area, and a sweep-in device. Dead chickens are identified using the YOLO v4 algorithm, an object detection network based on deep learning (Bochkovskiy et al., 2020; Redmon et al., 2016). The system exhibits high reliability, with accuracy, precision, and recall rates of 97.5 %, 95.24 %, and 100 %, respectively. However, recognizing dead chickens poses a challenge because the dead birds' shapes are incomplete and look very similar to a healthy chicken in a sitting or lying position. This similarity can impact the accuracy of image classification. To enhance precision and accuracy, the size of the training dataset for the model should be increased and identification errors should be reduced. Sensyn Robotics, Inc. (2023) developed a cage chicken house inspection robot that uses infrared thermal imaging to detect dead chickens. Hao et al. (2022) designed an autonomous inspection platform specifically for capturing images in stacked-cage broiler houses. Their study demonstrated that using this platform to collect images of broilers, combined with a dead broiler detection model, allows breeders to efficiently identify the location of deceased broilers within the broiler house. Lai et al. (2023) developed a robotic system to detect deceased chickens. This system uses a combination of robotic technology, infrared thermal imaging, and image processing to create an algorithm for identifying dead chickens, focusing on broilers housed in multi-tiered cages. The researchers tested this dead chicken detection system and reported an 83 % success rate in identifying dead chickens in the upper tier, a 77 % success rate in the lower tier, and an overall accuracy of 80 %. Lei et al. (2022) developed a multi-layer navigation system utilizing two robots to detect and remove broiler mortality. In this system, one robot is tasked with searching a large-scale workspace in a coverage mode to find and locate objects, while the second robot moves directly to the identified targets to remove

them. *Birds Eye Robotics* (2023) developed a robot designed to identify and pick up dead chickens. This robot employs a rotating shovel mechanism to collect the dead birds. Li et al. (2022a) developed a robot equipped with a camera and two grippers mounted at the end of a robotic arm, designed to remove dead chickens. The robotic arm (Gen 3, Kinova Inc., Boisbriand, QC, Canada), along with the camera and two grippers (Robotiq 2F-85, Kinova Inc., Boisbriand, QC, Canada) at the end, was securely mounted on a table. The robot underwent testing to assess its ability to grasp and lift dead chickens present on the table under varying light intensities. The robot arm has a maximum payload capacity of 2000 and can move with 7 degrees of freedom, allowing for versatile motion. The success rate of finding and collecting dead chickens was evaluated at different light intensities, resulting in rates of 53 %, 80 %, 87 %, 90 %, and 90 % at 10, 30, 60, 70, and 1000 light intensities, respectively. The robotic arm in question has been specifically engineered for the purpose of retrieving deceased chickens from a stationary table. It is important to note that this robotic arm has not yet undergone testing within the dynamic environment of a live poultry house. Furthermore, research findings reveal a noteworthy observation: a decrease in light intensity has been found to significantly impair the performance of the deep learning model. Specifically, this reduction in illumination adversely affects the model's capacity for object detection, image processing, orientation identification, and, ultimately, its ability to execute the final pick-up performance (Li et al., 2022a). Jan et al. (2022) presented a versatile poultry robot in their study, capable of patrolling poultry farms both within and outside the field of view. This robot can perform various tasks, including removing dead chicks, picking up floor eggs, turning over wet litter, and weighing birds. As discussed in Section 3.1, *Poultry Patrol* (2019) utilizes thermal imaging to monitor the body temperatures of chickens as it moves through the poultry house, enabling the identification of sick and dead birds. Similarly, the autonomous robot *Scout* (2023) employs an infrared and visible light camera to detect deceased chickens and diseases. Both systems monitor temperature and bird movements to identify sick and deceased animals in caged and cage-free systems. To ensure timely intervention for sick birds, these robots should be equipped with early warning systems.

Most existing robots capable of detecting sick birds lack the functionality for capturing and isolating the affected animals, leaving room for improvement. Furthermore, robots designed for the collection of dead birds are currently suitable for free-range systems. Since light intensities in poultry houses can vary due to factors like infrastructure and bird movements, an effective vision system is essential for these robots to accurately detect dead birds. In addition, in-ground rearing systems, especially equipment such as feeders and waterers may pose obstacles to identifying and collecting dead birds, so the movement flexibility of dead bird collection robots should be increased in closed areas around this equipment. One potential solution is the integration of flexible robotic arms and grippers to improve mobility and accessibility (Laschi et al., 2016; Althoefer, 2018; Frazier et al., 2020). Soft grippers (Fras et al., 2016; Hassan et al., 2019) are well-suited for this task due to their intrinsic safety and ability to naturally conform with the shape of the objects, facilitating the interaction with deformable and delicate objects in unstructured and cluttered environments. Soft tactile sensors could be added too (Mandil et al., 2023; Tomo et al., 2017; Ribeiro et al., 2017), further facilitating the effective localization (Chen et al., 2024) and safe handling of objects (Zenha et al., 2021) and possibly their recognition (Kirby et al., 2022) and characterization (Ribeiro et al., 2020), to verify that the picked object is the intended one. However, uncertainties remain regarding the performance of robotic arms for collecting dead birds under challenging poultry house conditions. Consequently, there is a pressing need to develop and refine robots tailored for the efficient collection of deceased birds.

3.3. Collecting floor eggs

The transition from cage system to cage-free systems aim to improve the welfare of laying hens (Ochs et al., 2019; Vroegindeweij et al., 2016) by providing them increased space for movement, perching, dustbathing, and nesting. This transition allows hens to spread their wings and express natural behaviours, ultimately leading to a reduction in confinement-related stress (Bhanja and Bhadauria, 2018; Hartcher and Jones, 2017). However, in cage-free systems hens may lay eggs in areas outside the nest, such as corners of the hen house and dim environments (Li et al., 2022b). While cage-free systems provide hens with various areas such as nests, perches, and litter (Hartcher and Jones, 2017), floor eggs are a common occurrence in these systems and reduce production performance (Oliveira et al., 2019). Automatic egg collection robots have been developed to address this issue, as described below.

Unlike commercial robots, scientific research on the use of robots in poultry farming has primarily focused on addressing the difficulty of collecting floor eggs as described in section 2.3. These robots can also reduce human-induced problems mentioned in section 2.4 by reducing the need for human labour in egg collection. Vroegindeweij et al. (2014b) developed an autonomous robot, *PoultryBot*, for collecting floor eggs in poultry houses. The robot, equipped with a spiral spring on the front for egg collection, successfully collected over 95 % of the eggs (Vroegindeweij et al., 2014b). This robot can drive autonomously for more than 3000 m in a commercial poultry house and collect 46 % of 300 eggs. A collection failure occurred in approximately 37 % of eggs (Vroegindeweij et al., 2018). The researchers suggested that by improving navigation, obstacle handling and control algorithms, the robot could be used in commercial poultry houses and dense animal environments in the future (Vroegindeweij et al., 2018; Vroegindeweij et al., 2014c).

Chang et al. (2020) designed a mobile egg collection robot using a computer vision-based platform that can recognize white and brown eggs in free-range farms. The robot moves toward the eggs with visual tracking, collects them, and stores them in its chamber. In experimental tests, the robot collected between 60 % and 88 % of the eggs on flat and surrounded floors. Additionally, the robot could collect 8 eggs in 10 min in a 25 m² area. For the robot to function efficiently, it relies on a flat surface free of objects such as egg-shaped stones within its operational area (Chang et al., 2020). Therefore, performance enhancements are necessary when deploying it in a free-range system.

Joffe and Usher (2017) developed *GohBot*, an autonomous egg-collecting robot that uses a mechanical arm with a vacuum mirror to collect eggs. In tests, the success rate of egg collection was 91.6 %. Li et al. (2021) developed an egg-collecting robot consisting of a deep learning-based egg detector, arm, gripper, and camera. Eggs detected by image processing algorithms are collected using the robot arm and grippers. The robot collected brown and white eggs with a success rate of 92 %–94 %. Wang et al. (2019) aimed to develop a livestock robot capable of picking and classifying eggs on farms. In their study, the robot utilized a special turntable and sliding mechanism to pick up, classify, and collect eggs from the ground.

Overall, egg collection robots developed for use in cage-free systems face general challenges, such as 1) mobility within the poultry house, including localization, navigation, path planning, and obstacle avoidance, 2) detecting eggs, 3) collecting eggs without breaking them, 4) storing eggs and possibly classifying them according to weight and shape.

3.4. Disinfection and litter management

The floor of the coop can become contaminated with bird faeces and food residues, leading to air pollution and the proliferation of pathogens. Regular cleaning and disinfection of the house are necessary to maintain animal health (Wu et al., 2022). Robots can be effectively used for smart production and appropriate disinfection in poultry houses (Feng et al.,

2021). Proper litter management is essential for poultry farming, and regular litter scraping can help aerate the litter, preventing fermentation and reducing litter moisture (Tibot, 2021). Robots designed for litter scraping can address litter management challenges (Section 2.2) and support animal health (Section 2.1).

Feng et al. (2021) designed an anti-epidemic (Feng et al., 2021) and disinfection spray (Feng and Wang, 2020) robot for use in poultry houses and farms. Comprising a robot, transport vehicle, sensors, spraying unit, and controller, it can work autonomously and with remote control. The researchers proposed the “Magnet-RFID” path detection navigation method for autonomous movement, which involves the manual installation of magnets and RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) electronic tags in the work area. The robot successfully ensured sufficient drug concentration in various parts of the cages to kill pathogenic microorganisms (Feng et al., 2021). Kunz Cechinel et al. (2024) designed a mobile robot platform for monitoring and sanitizing poultry litter. This platform is equipped with gas and soil sensors, allowing it to predict poultry diseases by measuring temperature, pH, humidity, and ammonia levels. As indicated in the product specifications, Octopus XO (2021), a multi-tasking robot, can autonomously move within the poultry house to scrape the litter and prevent the formation of scabs. It also reduces ammonia formation by providing better litter drying and performs litter cleaning by spraying a disinfectant solution. Spoutnic-NAV, another robot developed by Tibot, aerates the litter through the forks mounted on the back while moving in the poultry house (Tibot, 2021). Similarly, Poultry Patrol (2019) scrapes the litter while moving along the coop floor, promoting ventilation. Birds Eye Robotics (2023) features a spiked wheel system that helps the wheels grip the bedding ground securely, which enables the robot to turn over the bedding as it moves.

In floor-rearing systems for chickens, along with disinfection and regular turning of bedding as part of good litter management practices, adding fresh bedding over existing bedding is another approach used for maintaining cleanliness and managing waste in chicken houses. First-Pellets (2023) introduced an automated bedding laying robot utilizing a ceiling-mounted platform that spreads bedding using a rotating disc mechanism. This system can be remotely controlled and adjusted to alter the direction of bedding placement. Similarly, Poultry Matic Kft. (2023) developed the “PoultryMate” automatic bedding laying robot, which also employs a ceiling-mounted approach to automate the spreading of bedding. This automated method enhances efficiency and uniformity in bedding placement, thereby reducing bedding consumption. For more precise bedding placement, Inateco by Dussau (2023) engineered the “Sentinel” automatic bedding laying robot. Equipped with infrared thermal imaging and advanced sensing technologies, this robot employs artificial intelligence algorithms to detect and target areas with wet bedding. During operation, it monitors both the site and the chickens using additional sensors such as panoramic cameras and microphones.

To work successfully in the poultry house, these robots must have localization, navigation, and mobility capabilities without causing harm to the animals in cage-free systems. Another potential challenge for these robots is achieving effective litter scraping. Although robots have been developed for both caged and cage-free systems for sanitation and spraying, accurately determining the area and required amount of pesticide for spraying in the poultry house remains a difficulty.

3.5. Enhancing bird activity

Birds need physical activity to maintain their health and well-being. Inactive or sedentary behaviour for extended periods can lead to health issues in birds (Abbas et al., 2022). With the development of production systems characterized by rapid growth rates in broilers, fast-growing strains are used in commercial breeding (Zuidhof et al., 2014). It has been reported that faster-growing breeds have higher inactivity, behavioural traits are affected by the growth rate, and fast-growing breeds sit more, feed more, and walk less than slow-growing breeds

(Dawson et al., 2021; Hartcher and Lum, 2020). As higher activity can reduce litter contact, more active animals have been evaluated to have better feather cleanliness, lower hock burn levels and better leg health (Casey-Trott et al., 2017; Dixon, 2020; Hartcher and Lum, 2020). Robots have been shown to be effective in encouraging movement in broilers, leading to improved bone quality in animals (Hartcher and Jones, 2017; Janczak and Riber, 2015).

The two main approaches used in free-range poultry farms to encourage animal movement are mobile robots and laser pointers. Mobile ground robots that move within the poultry house trigger the animals around them to move as well (Li et al., 2022b; Tibot, 2021; T-Moov, 2022). Alternatively, robots with laser pointers project laser lights onto the floor, encouraging the birds to move (Scout, 2023). Tibot Technologies claim that their commercial autonomous mobile robots, T-Moov and Spoutnic NAV, increase bird activity in the poultry house and mitigate the issue of floor eggs in cage-free systems. Additionally, increased bird activity resulted in higher feed consumption and a natural weight gain of 300 g per animal. Moreover, active birds required fewer antibiotics to achieve weight gain naturally (Ren et al., 2020; Tibot, 2021; T-Moov, 2022). Marin et al. (2024) examined the short-term dynamics of changes in broiler spatial distribution within the robot’s zone of influence throughout the growing cycle. For this study, they utilized AviSense robot vehicles from Appellie Robotics (Córdoba, Argentina). The findings strongly suggest that, in addition to their role as environmental sensors, these robots effectively promoted increased movement in broilers throughout the growing cycle and encouraged additional exploratory behaviors.

The robot Octopus XO serves the dual purpose of litter cleaning while stimulating bird activity with laser pointers (Octopus XO, 2021). Similarly, the robot Scout (2023) has asserted its capability to stimulate animal activity through the utilization of laser pointers. Li et al. (2022b) reported that a ground robot designed to reduce floor eggs also effectively encouraged bird movement. Designed to monitor environmental conditions, RoboChick can also increase bird activity by encouraging the movement of chickens (Demmers et al., 2019). Another study by Yang et al. (2020) found that robots significantly increased the activity of broilers.

While robots have proven to increase activity in birds, ground robots face challenges such as improving autonomous mobility within the poultry house and obstacle avoidance. Addressing these issues is crucial for the successful implementation of ground robots in poultry farming. Additionally, further experimental data are needed to thoroughly evaluate the operational success of commercial robots. Overall, the use of robots to encourage bird activity in poultry farming holds great promise, and further research and development are essential to overcome existing challenges.

4. Robots for social interactions

4.1. Evaluation of robot-animal interactions

In this section, we discuss robotic research that examines the effects of robot-animal interactions on animal welfare and health (Table 2). Robotic studies have demonstrated that production, animal health, and welfare can be assessed by monitoring animals and poultry farms using cameras and sensors (section 3). A different topic is how robots designed for tasks that involve direct contact with animals affect their health and welfare.

Robots interacting with birds can have a positive effect by increasing their activity levels (see section 3.5). This increased activity can enhance foot health and maintain feather condition by reducing the time spent on the ground (Yang et al., 2020). Nonetheless, there are concerns about the potential stresses arising from robot-animal interactions (Parajuli et al., 2020). As mobile ground robots move, they may inadvertently hit, physically harm or frighten the birds (Dennis et al., 2020). Fear is a natural response to perceived danger, serving as an adaptive mechanism

Table 2
Robots for animal interaction and social interaction.

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of cited robotic researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target animal	Robots
Animal health and welfare (sec. 2.1)	Robot-animal interaction (sec. 4.1) Cited rob. res:7	Reducing animal stress and fear – Observe behaviour – Measure distance (Avoidance distance tests)	Mobile Robot	Dennis et al., 2020	Broiler	
			Robotic Vehicle (RV)- Lynx motion	Parajuli et al., 2018, 2020	Hen + broiler	
			Ground robot	Li et al., 2022b	Broiler	
			Mobile Robotic Prototype Robotic Vehicle	Balthazar et al., 2024 Yang et al., 2020	Broiler Hen + broiler	
	Provide social interaction (sec. 4.2) Cited rob. res:4	Imprinting – Movement – Sound – Colour – Size – Heat source	PoulBot	Gribovskiy et al., 2018	Chick	
			Robo-Chick	Slonina et al., 2021	Chicks	

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Poultry issue	Farming task to solve (Number of cited robotic researches)	Desired general features	Robotic solution already available	Reference	Target animal	Robots
			Robot (Jolly et al., 2016)	Jolly et al., 2016	Chicks	
			Robot (de Margerie et al., 2011)	de Margerie et al., 2011	Quail chicks	

to protect animals from potential harm (Jones, 1996). However, fear-induced responses can lead to panic reactions, piling, smothering, lameness, and bone damage, such as keel bone damage, which are common welfare problems in cage-free systems (Edgar et al., 2016; Widowski and Rentsch, 2022). Animal behaviour studies on the natural behaviour repertoire of a species can help to identify proxies for fear or adaptation to external stimuli (Fraser, 2009; Mench, 1998; Meuser et al., 2021). Animal behaviour studies can encompass various aspects, including behavioural proxies such as avoidance, exploration, activity levels, and panic reactions (Fraser, 2009; Mench, 1998; Meuser et al., 2021); physiological proxies such as corticosterone levels, feather condition, heart rate, lameness and bone damage (Edgar et al., 2013; Jacobs et al., 2023; Mikoni et al., 2023; Wilcox et al., 2023; Sahan et al., 2006) and other measurement such as vocalizations (Li et al., 2020b; Olczak et al., 2023; Siegford et al., 2023). Avoidance behaviour in animals is considered a response to fear (Brantsæter et al., 2016; Christensen et al., 2021; Olsson et al., 2019; Versace et al., 2021). Conversely, exploration signifies the recognition of the environment, a reduced fear response, and the ability to adapt to new stimuli (Agnvall et al., 2014; Jones, 1996). Monitoring these behaviours can help assess animal welfare (Meuser et al., 2021; Vroegindewij et al., 2014a).

Avoidance distance tests, which can be employed to detect fear and exploration behaviours during interactions with robots (Parajuli et al., 2020; Vroegindewij et al., 2014a), are essential for understanding how animals adapt to robots, including studying behaviours such as fear responses and restlessness (Li et al., 2022b). Several studies have evaluated avoidance behaviour within the scope of investigating the effects of robot-animal interactions on birds. Dennis et al. (2020) have compared the response of birds to walking humans and mobile robots simulating commercial rearing conditions for broilers over a 6-week period, concluding that those robots could safely operate among the broiler flock. Animal behaviour was evaluated through camera images as the robot moved along a fixed route inside the coop three times a day. The farmer used the same route for daily work in the poultry house. While the broilers' activity increased during the robot's motion, the increase was lower compared to human observations. Startling behaviour in broilers was also found to be low. The study highlighted that early exposure to robots might lead to habituation and reduced fear in animals. Moreover, startling behaviours like flapping and jumping were not observed before 9 days of age, emphasizing the importance of early exposure to minimize physical harm to birds. The researchers also noted that as chicks grow older and their body sizes increase, there are challenges in the operation of the robot due to the reduced available space

for movement.

Parajuli et al. (2018) evaluated the avoidance distances of laying hens and broilers of different ages in response to a robot for bird-robot interactions. Avoidance distances tended to decrease for both laying hens and broilers at older ages. Human-robot interactions were also evaluated by measuring avoidance behaviour (Butterworth et al., 2009). The study also involved a comparison between robot-animal interactions and human-animal interactions (Parajuli et al., 2018). The overall avoidance distances observed in human-animal interactions were shorter than in robot-animal interactions, suggesting better interactions between animals and humans. However, all tested birds had daily exposure to humans before the avoidance distance test, while their exposure to a robot occurred only on the test day. This difference in exposure may have influenced the outcomes. Researchers attributed the avoidance behaviour towards the robot to its sound and speed, suggesting that these aspects should be optimized in future robots (Parajuli et al., 2018, 2020).

Balthazar et al. (2024) investigated how broiler chickens responded to the presence of a robot by measuring their escape distances. They tested two different robot movement speeds. In the first treatment, where the robot moved at a slower speed, chickens exhibited shorter escape distances but experienced more collisions with the robot. In the second treatment, with the robot moving at a higher speed, chickens had longer escape distances and fewer collisions. It was confirmed that the escape distance is influenced by the robot's speed, but an inverse relationship was found regarding the number of collisions, indicating that slower robot speeds led to more frequent collisions (Balthazar et al., 2024).

Li et al. (2022b) evaluated the impact of a ground robot designed to reduce floor eggs on various production indicators, including egg production, feed consumption, and mortality. They also measured common physiological stress indicators (e.g., serum corticosterone concentration), to assess the potential stress induced by the robot on the animals. Additionally, given that ground robots were shown to promote bird activity (see Section 3.5), the research also examined bone quality and nesting behaviour. The experiment comprised three groups: a group with no robot, a group with 1 week of exposure to the robot, and a group with 2 weeks of exposure to the robot. For each flock, the experiment extended over ten weeks, divided into two phases. Phase 1 spanned from weeks 35–39, while Phase 2 covered weeks 40 to 43. The results indicated that the robot treatments did not induce stress in the birds and did not have a statistically significant effect on production performance. Furthermore, the study concluded that although ground robots

encouraged bird movement, there were no significant differences in bone quality and nesting behaviour (Li et al., 2022b). It's worth noting that robot manipulation periods of 1 week and 2 weeks may not be sufficient to affect production performance, stress responses, and bone quality. Therefore, it may be recommended to evaluate the longer-term effect of robot manipulation and investigate its effects throughout the entire production period.

Yang et al. (2020) investigated the effects of robots interacting with broilers on broiler production performance, gait score, paw quality, plumage cleanliness, and activities. They used a robot manipulated by a remote controller for the research. The use of robots was found to significantly increase broiler activity, and no negative effects were observed on production performance. These studies evaluated robot-animal interactions for automation and precision management applications in poultry production. Early initiation of robot-animal interactions can lead to reduced fear and faster exploratory behaviour, promoting earlier adaptability. Nevertheless, it remains unclear how robotic applications might elicit responses in birds of different ages. Future research needs to determine the optimal usage times of robots in broiler houses, considering the decreased mobility of robots and restricted activities of animals at advanced ages. Additionally, there is a research gap in understanding how visual, auditory, and mobility features contribute to the exploration and adaptation process for animals becoming accustomed to robots. Examining features such as the size, colour, movement speed, and sound of the robot can shed light on this aspect. Moreover, more information is needed on robot design to prevent injuries in case of physical contact with animals.

4.2. Social interactions

High-capacity brooder machines are used in commercial poultry farming to produce chicks. However, the chicks hatched in incubators are reared separately from the mother hens (Edgar et al., 2016), depriving them of natural stimuli that influence their behaviour and social learning (Roden and Wechsler, 1998). This section focuses on hen-chick interaction to understand the learning process in chicks raised with mother hens and the development of robots to promote social learning in the absence of the mother hen.

Chicks raised by mother hens in natural conditions learn from their mothers about behaviour, pecking habits, resting times, and food preferences (Edgar et al., 2016). Studies evaluating hen-chick interactions have shown that chicks reared with mother hens exhibit synchronization in activity and resting behaviours. They spend less time standing, more time feeding, and less time on perches compared to chicks raised without a mother (Roden and Wechsler, 1998). In the absence of a mother, chicks tend to display more fear behaviour and engage in feather pecking, leading to welfare issues like panic reactions and broken bones in animals (Edgar et al., 2016). Feather pecking is a behavioural issue in which hens engaged in the unwanted behaviour of pecking at, plucking, or pulling out the feathers of other hens within the same flock (Nicol, 2019). This behaviour, if left unmanaged, can result in feather damage, skin injuries, and may even escalate to cannibalism (Cronin and Glatz, 2020; EFSA AHAW Panel, 2023; Göransson et al., 2023; Kaukonen and Valros, 2019; Özentürk et al., 2022). It is a significant welfare concern in the poultry farming industry and may be improved by social learning mechanisms (Roden and Wechsler, 1998). Social learning mechanisms, based on filial imprinting, play a crucial role in shaping chick behaviours (Nicol, 2015). Filial imprinting refers to the fast-learning process that enables animals to quickly learn the features of objects by mere exposure (without explicit reward) and become attached to them (Vallortigara and Versace, 2022) at the beginning of life. Social attachment is shown for instance by following responses and distress calls upon separation from the imprinting object. Chicks are excellent subjects for studying spontaneous social interactions and social interactions that follow filial imprinting (Rosa-Salva et al., 2021; Versace et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024). In natural conditions, imprinting

enables chicks to interact with their mother hens, but in the absence of the mother, they may easily imprint on artificial objects that do not have naturalistic appearance (Rosa-Salva et al., 2018; Rosa-Salva et al., 2021; Versace et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2024; Wood and Wood, 2015). Hence, the development of robots for social interaction with poultry chicks is facilitated by the fact that chicks can imprint also on non-naturalistic objects. Research on early predispositions (spontaneous preferences apparent at birth or hatching), is uncovering how simple features, such as upward movement (Bliss et al., 2023), and face-like patterns (Rosa-Salva et al., 2010) can trigger social attraction in poultry chicks (Lemaire and Vallortigara, 2023; Rosa-Salva et al., 2021; Versace et al., 2018). Research has also noted that chicks prefer patterned objects (Mondada et al., 2013), coloured objects (with red and blue being attractive colours) (Ham and Osorio, 2007) and moving objects (Bateson and Jaekel, 1974; Versace et al., 2019). Auditory stimuli also play a crucial role in the imprinting process (Bolhuis and Van Kampen, 1991).

Robotic research aims to improve collective and social behaviour by allowing robots to interact with chicks and support their social learning and development (de Margerie et al., 2011). Using robots as social partners is a promising novel approach to studying animal behaviour, with the primary goal of imprinting chicks on robots that can facilitate healthy behaviour.

Robotic research has explored interactions between robots and chicks in laboratory settings based on the imprinting mechanism (de Margerie et al., 2011; Gribovskiy et al., 2018; Jolly et al., 2016; Slonina et al., 2021) (Table 2). For instance, Gribovskiy et al. (2018) designed an autonomous mobile robot called PoulBot to study collective and social behaviour in chickens. The robot, through its filial imprinting mechanism, was successfully recognized as a congener leader by the chicks, and social integration was demonstrated experimentally. Slonina et al. (2021) developed the RoboChick to identify features that promote the filial imprinting mechanism in chicks. The robot's attractiveness was tested using flashing lights and vocalizations for robot-chick interactions, which did not induce fear in chicks and proved suitable for other experiments. Jolly et al. (2016) examined the social learning mechanism in groups of quail chicks exposed/not exposed to a robot. After spending 3 days together, the chicks exhibited more synchronized activities after early exposure to the robot. Moreover, chicks made more distress calls upon separation from the robot. de Mergerie et al. (2011) used an autonomous robot to evaluate early spatial experiences in quail chicks, finding that animals were motivated to interact spatially with the robot.

Considering the large number of chicks raised separately from mother hens in commercial poultry breeding, these laboratory experiments hold significant potential in the development of robots for poultry farming. However, social interaction research using robots-animal studies is still limited. Nevertheless, with advancements in the perceptual abilities, autonomy, and capabilities of robots, they are expected to be widely used in the future. Furthermore, the development of animal behaviour based on robots' social learning mechanisms can contribute to the improvement of animal welfare.

5. Current limitations and future directions of research

In this section, we discuss the current general limitations and future directions of research in robots for poultry, focusing on different functions. Compared to the scale of poultry farming, scientific research, open-source and commercial robots are still limited (Abbas et al., 2022). To assess the operational success of these robots, it is essential to conduct experimental research and share data on the effectiveness and reliability of different robotic systems able support an industry that has a pivotal socioeconomic role worldwide.

Overall, robots for poultry farming are still limited in functionality and adaptability, since most robots are designed to perform a single, specific task (Ren et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022). Hence, research should expand multi-tasking abilities, via sensor integration and advanced

technology, including AI (Alatise and Hancke, 2020; Yang et al., 2024). For instance, in the context of collecting floor eggs and managing dead birds, robots face several challenges. These include difficulties in accessing different locations within the poultry house, issues with target identification and capture due to factors such as poultry house infrastructure, bird movements, changing light intensities, and secluded areas. Moreover, robots designed to collect floor eggs encounter challenges in collecting eggs without breakage, as well as sorting and storing them (Chang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2022b; Vroegindeweij et al., 2018). To address these challenges, robots should be designed to operate effectively across various environmental conditions and production systems. To this aim, reliability of visual and tactile perception, combined with flexibility and safety of the movements, are particularly important. The development of algorithms related to object detection, localisation, navigation, path planning, and control is essential. Some robots can be operated manually and by remote control (Li, 2016; Yang et al., 2020), however, there is a need for autonomous work, reducing the need for constant manual or remote control. Visuo-tactile perception is crucial for autonomous robotic systems, especially if they have to grasp and manipulate objects (Navarro-Guerrero et al., 2023).

An important issue is the difficulty in avoiding obstacles while navigating within the poultry house (Dennis et al., 2020; Vroegindeweij et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2024). During the movement of robots, the unpredictable actions of the surrounding chickens can impact the detection of static obstacles. Simultaneously, the robots need to make necessary evasive maneuvers with respect to the moving chickens. These requirements impose a high demand on the robot's environmental perception capability and real-time path planning when confronting mobility-related challenges (see Section 2) including those associated with production and human-induced factors. It will be crucial to develop obstacle awareness systems to improve navigation and guarantee animal welfare.

Most studies on robotic applications in poultry farming have primarily focused on free-range systems. However, robots that come into direct contact with animals pose a risk of harming animals and, as a result, may operate at a slower pace (Abbas et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022). To mitigate these risks and challenges, robots should be designed with the ability to avoid and regulate contact. A current solution is non-contact systems, such as those involving robotic arms mounted on the ceiling of the farm. However, these systems can hardly be implemented in existing farms and would require restructuring or building of dedicated facilities, complicating the logistics of implementation. Hardware solutions to reduce the risks of robot harming animals include protective equipment, such as robots built with soft materials.

In some situations, robot-animal contact is necessary. In cases where robots are deployed for the identification of sick birds, an additional capability for capturing and isolating animals has been shown to be viable when employed within an operational poultry farm in conjunction with the detection system (Liu et al., 2021). For enhanced welfare and biosecurity, robots should also incorporate an early warning system to promptly intervene in cases involving sick birds.

Poultry farms differ in size and organisation (Ren et al., 2020). However, most robotic studies are conducted in controlled experimental environments or within small-scale poultry houses (Vroegindeweij et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). Further tests and development are needed for large-capacity poultry houses, including tests on the integration of multiple robots to working together efficiently, in accordance with the size of the poultry house.

Effective and safe robot-animal interactions require knowledge of the species-specific needs in terms of social interactions. Research has just started to address these areas, with few studies that identify social learning mechanisms that can improve welfare and health in interactions with robots (Gribovskiy et al., 2018; Mostafavi et al., 2010). Further research is needed to understand how robots can be best integrated in commercial farms, from the point of view of hardware design and functionality.

Robot-animal interactions present opportunities and challenges. Ground-based robotic systems offer a promising avenue for enhancing animal mobility, with potential benefits for chicken welfare. Such benefits include a reduction in litter contact (Dixon, 2020; Hartcher and Lum, 2020), an improvement in bone quality (Hartcher and Jones, 2017; Janczak and Riber, 2015), as well as enhancement in foot health and feather condition (Yang et al., 2020).

At the same time, robots increase birds' energy consumption, with effects that have just started to be investigated. It has been suggested that this activity might reduce egg nutrient accumulation in laying hens and decrease egg weight (Li et al., 2022b). Future research should target various parameters such as food consumption, egg weight and food conversion rate to assess the effect of robot use on overall yield in commercial poultry farming.

Potential stress arising from interactions between robots and animals, and whether robots pose lower or higher challenges to animals, are object of research. Ground robots, as they move around poultry houses, exhibit the potential to reduce the incidence of startling behaviour compared to human breeders, while simultaneously mitigating the risk of disease transmission within the poultry house (Park et al., 2022). Differences of responses to robots within the life course have not been investigated enough (Parajuli et al., 2018). Remarkably, research has revealed that chickens exhibit a propensity to form attachments to non-naturalistic agents, such as robots (Gribovskiy et al., 2018; Slonina et al., 2021). Furthermore, early exposure to robots can effectively mitigate fear reactions towards these artificial agents (Dennis et al., 2020).

The use of robots can be costly, especially for small-scale coops operations (Abbas et al., 2022; Mamun, 2019). It is crucial to conduct economic analyses to assess the viability of using robots in poultry houses. Such analyses should consider their potential effects on human labour, animal health, and production output to make informed decisions about investment.

Creating robots tailored for various functions in poultry farming demands a collaborative approach that delves into multiple domains, such as mechanical engineering, software development, data analytics, genetic animal breeding, animal behaviour, and animal welfare (Zhou et al., 2022). This diverse integration of specialized knowledge is essential in designing robotic solutions that precisely address the intricate demands of poultry farming, ensuring optimal performance, operational efficiency and animal well-being.

6. Conclusion

The exploration of robotic technology for poultry farming has enormous promise awaiting realization. The current research landscape, though limited, indicates the potential for robots to innovate poultry farming, reducing labour dependency and significantly enhancing management efficiency by aiding in animal and environmental monitoring. However, this potential has only just begun to be tapped. Further research is needed to fully harness the benefits of robotics in supporting efficient production and promoting animal welfare.

As the poultry industry embraces the integration with robotics, the critical aspects of robot-animal interactions must be considered. Effective solutions require at the same time engineering innovation and a thorough understanding of animal needs and behaviour, as shown by research on imprinting and predispositions in poultry chicks (Rosa-Salva et al., 2021; Versace et al., 2018) and adult chickens (Dennis et al., 2020; Nicol, 2023). One of the challenges ahead involves the need for increased data sharing and open-source development. Addressing these challenges is crucial for understanding and achieving animal welfare. Overall, the integration of robotic technology and innovation with a deep understanding of animal needs and societal demands is an opportunity for enhancing both productivity and welfare in poultry farming.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Uğur Özentürk: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Zhengqi Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Lorenzo Jamone:** Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Elisabetta Versace:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by International Postdoctoral Research Scholarship Program (No. 2219) of the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye, China Scholarship Council (No. 202208060081), Royal Society Leverhulme Trust fellowship (SRF\R1\21000155: Generalisation using sparse data: from animal to artificial systems) and Leverhulme the effectTrust research grant RPG-2020-287 (Generalisation from limited experience: how to solve the problem of induction).

References

- Abbas, G., Jaffery, S., Hashmi, A.H., Tanveer, A.J., Arshad, M., Amin, Q.A., Saeed, M.I., Saleem, M., Qureshi, R.A.M., Khan, A.A., Alvi, M.A., Mustafa, A., Qamar, S.H., Iqbal, T.A., Shabbir, S.B., Ashraf, M., Ahmad, F., Iqbal, A., Abbas, S., Mahboob, U., Hassan, M.U., Khan, R.U., Abbas, H., Sultan, Z., Al-Taey, D.K., Rehman, M.S., Tayyab, M., Shaikat, B., Zafar, M.R., 2022. Prospects and challenges of adopting and implementing smart technologies in poultry production. *Pak. J. Sci.* 74 (2).
- Abeyesinghe, S.M., Chancellor, N.M., Moore, D.H., Chang, Y.-M., Pearce, J., Demmers, T., Nicol, C.J., 2021. Associations between behaviour and health outcomes in conventional and slow-growing breeds of broiler chicken. *Animal* 15, 100261.
- Aggrey, S.E., 2009. Logistic nonlinear mixed effects model for estimating growth parameters. *Poult. Sci.* 88, 276–280.
- Agnvall, B., Ali, A., Olby, S., Jensen, P., 2014. Red Junglefowl (*Gallus gallus*) selected for low fear of humans are larger, more dominant and produce larger offspring. *Animal* 8, 1498–1505.
- Ahmad, I., Ullah, M., Alkafay, M., Ahmed, N., Mahmoud, S.F., Sohail, K., Ullah, H., Ghoneim, W.M., Ahmed, M.M., Sayed, S., 2022. Identification of the economic composition, and supplementation of maggot meal in broiler production. *Saudi J. Biol. Sci.* 29, 103277.
- Alatise, M.B., Hancke, G.P., 2020. A Review on Challenges of Autonomous Mobile Robot and Sensor Fusion Methods. *IEEE Access* 8, 39830–39846. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2975643>.
- Althoefer, K., 2018. Antagonistic actuation and stiffness control in soft inflatable robots. *Nat. Rev. Mater.* 3 (6), 76–77.
- Aral, Y., Arikkan, M.S., Unbasilar, E.E., Unal, N., Gokdai, A., Erdem, E., 2017. Economic comparison of unenriched and alternative cage systems used in laying hen husbandry-recent experience under Turkish commercial conditions. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 73, 69–76.
- Astill, J., Dara, R.A., Fraser, E.D., Roberts, B., Sharif, S., 2020. Smart poultry management: smart sensors, big data, and the internet of things. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 170, 105291.
- Attia, Y.A., Rahman, M.T., Hossain, M.J., Basiouni, S., Khafaga, A.F., Shehata, A.A., Hafez, H.M., 2022. Poultry production and sustainability in developing countries under the COVID-19 crisis: lessons learned. *Animals* 12, 644.
- Balthazar, G.D.R., Silveira, R.M.F., Silva, I.J.O.D., 2024. How do escape distance behavior of broiler chickens change in response to a mobile robot moving at two different speeds? *Animals* 14, 1–12.
- Bateson, P.P.G., Jaekel, J.B., 1974. Imprinting: correlations between activities of chicks during training and testing. *Anim. Behav.* 22, 899–906.
- Bhanja, S.K., Bhadauria, P., 2018. Behaviour and welfare concepts in laying hens and their association with housing systems.
- Birds Eye Robotics, 2023. <https://www.birdseyerobotics.com/> (accessed 16 July 2024).
- Bliss, L., Vasas, V., Freeland, L., Roach, R., Ferré, E.R., Versace, E., 2023. A spontaneous gravity prior: newborn chicks prefer stimuli that move against gravity. *Biol. Lett.* 19 (2), 20220502.
- Bochkovskiy, A., Wang, C.-Y., Liao, H.-Y.M., 2020. Yolov4: Optimal speed and accuracy of object detection. *ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv200410934*.
- Bolhuis, J.J., 1991. Mechanisms of avian imprinting: a review. *Biol. Rev.* 66, 303–345.
- Bolhuis, J.J., Van Kampen, H.S., 1991. Auditory learning and filial imprinting in the chick. *Behaviour* 117, 303–319.
- Brantsæter, M., Tahamtani, F.M., Moe, R.O., Hansen, T.B., Orritt, R., Nicol, C., Janczak, A.M., 2016. Rearing laying hens in aviaries reduces fearfulness following transfer to furnished cages. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 3, 13.
- Buijs, S., Booth, F., Richards, G., McGaughey, L., Nicol, C.J., Edgar, J., Tarlton, J.F., 2018. Behavioural and physiological responses of laying hens to automated monitoring equipment. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 199, 17–23.
- Buijs, S., Nicol, C.J., Booth, F., Richards, G., Tarlton, J.F., 2020. Light-based monitoring devices to assess range use by laying hens. *Animal* 14, 814–823.
- Butterworth, A., Arnould, C., Niekerk, T.F., 2009. Assessment protocol for poultry. Welfare Quality Consortium Lelystad, The Netherlands.
- Carenzi, C., Verga, M., 2009. Animal welfare: review of the scientific concept and definition. *Ital. J. Anim. Sci.* 8, 21–30.
- Casey-Trott, T.M., Korver, D.R., Guerin, M.T., Sandilands, V., Torrey, S., Widowski, T.M., 2017. Opportunities for exercise during pullet rearing, Part II: long-term effects on bone characteristics of adult laying hens at the end-of-lay. *Poult. Sci.* 96, 2518–2527.
- Chai, L., 2022. Robots for Precision Poultry and Egg Production. *Precision Poultry Farming* <https://site.caes.uga.edu/precisionpoultry/2022/08/robots-for-precision-poultry-and-egg-production/> (accessed 21 February 2023).
- Chang, C.-L., Xie, B.-X., Wang, C.-H., 2020. Visual guidance and egg collection scheme for a smart poultry robot for free-range farms. *Sensors* 20, 6624.
- Chen Z., Versace, E., Jamone, L., 2024. 3D Localization of Objects Buried within Granular Materials Using a Distributed 3-Axis Tactile Sensor. In: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*.
- Chicken Nannies, 2017. Chicken nannies are all the rage in China. <https://www.farmprgress.com/farm-life/chicken-nannies-are-all-the-rage-in-china> (accessed 23 February 2023).
- Christensen, J.W., Ahrendt, L.P., Malmkvist, J., Nicol, C., 2021. Exploratory behaviour towards novel objects is associated with enhanced learning in young horses. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 1428.
- Costantini, M., Ferrante, V., Guarino, M., Bacenetti, J., 2021. Environmental sustainability assessment of poultry productions through life cycle approaches: a critical review. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 110, 201–212.
- Cronin, G.M., Glatz, P.C., 2020. Causes of feather pecking and subsequent welfare issues for the laying hen: a review. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 61 (10), 990–1005.
- Dawson, L.C., Widowski, T.M., Liu, Z., Edwards, A.M., Torrey, S., 2021. In pursuit of a better broiler: a comparison of the inactivity, behavior, and enrichment use of fast- and slower growing broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 100, 101451.
- de Margerie, E., Lumineau, S., Houdelier, C., Yris, M.R., 2011. Influence of a mobile robot on the spatial behaviour of quail chicks. *Bioinspir. Biomim.* 6, 034001.
- de Mesquita Souza Saraiva, M., Lim, K., do Monte, D.F.M., Givisiez, P.E.N., Alves, L.B.R., de Freitas Neto, O.C., Kariuki, S., Júnior, A.B., de Oliveira, C.J.B., Gebreyes, W.A., 2022. Antimicrobial resistance in the globalized food chain: A One Health perspective applied to the poultry industry. *Braz. J. Microbiol.* 1–22.
- Demmers, T.G.M., Dennis, I.C., Norman, P., Butler, M., Clare, D., 2019. RoboChick: An autonomous roving platform for data collection in poultry buildings, operational parameters and bird behaviour. In: *Proc of the 9th European Conference on Precision Livestock Farming*, pp. 414–420.
- Dennis, I.C., Abeyesinghe, S.M., Demmers, T.G.M., 2020. The behaviour of commercial broilers in response to a mobile robot. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 61, 483–492.
- Dixon, L.M., 2020. Slow and steady wins the race: the behaviour and welfare of commercial faster growing broiler breeds compared to a commercial slower growing breed. *PLoS One* 15, e0231006.
- Dogan, N., Kaygisiz, F., Altinel, A., 2018. Technical and economic efficiency of laying hen farms in Konya, Turkey. *Braz. J. Poult. Sci.* 20, 263–272.
- Edgar, J., Held, S., Jones, C., Troisi, C., 2016. Influences of maternal care on chicken welfare. *Animals* 6, 2.
- Edgar, J.L., Paul, E.S., Nicol, C.J., 2013. Protective mother hens: cognitive influences on the avian maternal response. *Anim. Behav.* 86, 223–229.
- EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Animal Welfare), Nielsen, S.S., Alvarez, J., Bicout, D.J., Calistri, P., Canali, E., Drewe, J.A., Garin-Bastuji, B., Gonzales Rojas, J.L., Gortázar Schmidt, C., Herskin, M., Miranda Chueca, M.A., Padalino, B., Pasquali, P., Roberts, H.C., Spoolder, H., Stahl, K., Velarde, A., Viltrop, A., Winckler, C., Estevez, I., Guinebreffere, M., Rodenburg, B., Schrader, L., Tiemann, I., Van Niekerk, T., Ardizzone, M., Ashe, S., Hempen, M., Mosbach-Schulz, O., Gimeno Rojo, C., Van der Stede, Y., Vitali, M., Michel, V., 2023. Scientific opinion on the welfare of laying hens on farm. *EFSA J.*, 21 (2023), p. 7789, 188.
- ElZanaty, H., 2014. A Techno-Economic study for heating poultry houses using renewable energy [master's Thesis, the American University in Cairo]. AUC Knowledge Fountain. <https://fount.aucegypt.edu/etds/123>.
- Feng, Q., Wang, B., Zhang, W., Li, X., 2021. Development and Test of Spraying Robot for Anti-epidemic and Disinfection in Animal Housing, in *2021 WRC Symposium on Advanced Robotics and Automation (WRC SARA)*. *IEEE*, pp. 24–29.
- Feng, Q.C., Wang, X., 2020. Design of disinfection robot for livestock breeding. *Procedia Comput. Sci.* 166, 310–314.
- Fernyhough, M., Nicol, C.J., van de Braak, T., Toscano, M.J., Tonnessen, M., 2020. The ethics of laying hen genetics. *J. Agric. Environ. Ethics* 33, 15–36.
- Ferreira, V.H.B., Germain, K., Calandreau, L., Guesdon, V., 2020. Range use is related to free-range broiler chickens' behavioral responses during food and social conditioned place preference tests. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 230, 105083.

- FirstPellets, Firstlit – Distributeur Automatique De Litière - © 2023 Firstpellets, <https://www.farinepaille.fr/nos-produits-farine-miette-de-paille/firstlit-miette-de-paille/>. (accessed 12 July 2024).
- Flora, G.D., Sandhiya, R., Santhiya, P., Sindhu, G., Sribavatharani, K.G., Ramani, U., 2022. Smart Monitoring Instrumentation design for poultry farmhouse. In: 2022 7th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES). IEEE, pp. 1551–1554.
- Fras, J., Maciás, M., Czubaczyński, F., Salek P., Główska, J., 2016. Soft Flexible Gripper Design, Characterization and Application (pp. 368-377). In Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering (Vol. 543, pp. 368-377). Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-48923-0_40.
- Fraser, D., 2009. Animal behaviour, animal welfare and the scientific study of affect. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 118, 108–117.
- Frazier, P.A., Jamone, L., Althoefer, K., Calvo, P., 2020. Plant bioinspired ecological robotics. *Front. Robotics and AI* 7, 79.
- George, A.S., 2024. Humanoid robots as poultry partners: enhancing welfare through collaboration on the farm. *Partners Universal International Research Journal* 3 (1), 183–199.
- Gerber, P.J., Mottet, A., Opio, C.I., Falcucci, A., Teillard, F., 2015. Environmental impacts of beef production: review of challenges and perspectives for durability. *Meat Sci.* 109, 2–12.
- Gittins, P., McElwee, G., Tipi, N., 2020. Discrete event simulation in livestock management. *J. Rural Stud.* 78, 387–398.
- Göransson, L., Abeyesinghe, S., Yngvesson, J., Gunnarsson, S., 2023. How are they really doing? Animal welfare on organic laying hen farms in terms of health and behaviour. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 64, 552–564.
- Gribovskiy, A., Halloy, J., Deneubourg, J.-L., Mondada, F., 2018. Designing a socially integrated mobile robot for ethological research. *Robot. Auton. Syst.* 103, 42–55.
- Guerrero, N., Toprak, S., Josifovski, J., Jamone, L., 2023. Visuo-haptic object perception for robots: an overview. *Auton. Robots* 47, 377–403.
- Gunnarsson, S., Arvidsson Segerkvist, K., Göransson, L., Hansson, H., Sonesson, U., 2020. Systematic mapping of research on farm-level sustainability in egg and chicken meat production. *Sustainability* 12, 3033.
- Hafez, H.M., Attia, Y.A., 2020. Challenges to the poultry industry: current perspectives and strategic future after the COVID-19 outbreak. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 7, 516.
- Ham, A.D., Osorio, D., 2007. Colour preferences and colour vision in poultry chicks. *Proc. r. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 274, 1941–1948.
- Hao, H., Fang, P., Duan, E., Yang, Z., Wang, L., Wang, H., 2022. A dead broiler inspection system for large-scale breeding farms based on deep learning. *Agriculture* 12 (8), 1176.
- Hartcher, K.M., Jones, B., 2017. The welfare of layer hens in cage and cage-free housing systems. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 73, 767–782.
- Hartcher, K.M., Lum, H.K., 2020. Genetic selection of broilers and welfare consequences: a review. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 76, 154–167.
- Hassan, A., Godaba, H., Althoefer, K., 2019. Design Analysis of a Fabric-Based Lightweight Robotic Gripper. In: Althoefer, K., Konstantinova, J., Zhang, K. (Eds.), *Towards Autonomous Robotic Systems, TAROS 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Vol. 11649. Springer, pp. 1–10. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-23807-0_2.
- Inateco by Dussau, Sentinel automatic bedding Robot - © 2023 Inateco by Dussau, <https://www.inateco.eu/sentinel-automatic-bedding-robot/?lang=en>. (accessed 12 July 2024).
- Jacobs, L., Blatchford, R.A., De Jong, I.C., Erasmus, M.A., Levengood, M., Newberry, R. C., Regmi, P., Riber, A.B., Weimer, S.L., 2023. Enhancing their quality of life: environmental enrichment for poultry. *Poult. Sci.* 102, 102233.
- Jan, M.S., Ke, J.Y., Chang, C.L., 2022. Integrated positioning method based on UWB and RTK-GNSS for seamless navigation of poultry robots. In: 2022 International Automatic Control Conference (CACCS). IEEE, pp. 1–6.
- Janczak, A.M., Riber, A.B., 2015. Review of rearing-related factors affecting the welfare of laying hens. *Poult. Sci.* 94, 1454–1469.
- Joffe, B.P., Usher, C.T., 2017. In: *Autonomous robotic system for picking up floor eggs in poultry houses*. ASABE Annual International Meeting. American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers, p. 1.
- Jolly, L., Pittet, F., Caudal, J.-P., Mouret, J.-B., Houdelier, C., Lumineau, S., de Margerie, E., 2016. Animal-to-robot social attachment: initial requisites in a gallinaceous bird. *Bioinspir. Biomim.* 11, 016007.
- Jones, R.B., 1996. Fear and adaptability in poultry: insights, implications, and imperatives. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 52, 131–174.
- Kaukonen, E., Valros, A., 2019. Feather pecking and cannibalism in non-beak-trimmed laying hen flocks—Farmers’ perspectives. *Animals* 9 (2), 43.
- Kaur, U., Voyles, R.M., Donkin, S., 2021. Future of Animal Welfare—Technological Innovations for Individualized Animal Care. *Improv. Anim. Welf.* 570.
- Kirby, E., Zenha, R., Jamone, L., 2022. Comparing single touch to dynamic exploratory procedures for robotic tactile object recognition. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 7 (2), 4252–4258.
- Kleyn, F.J., Ciacciariello, M., 2021. Future demands of the poultry industry: will we meet our commitments sustainably in developed and developing economies? *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 77, 267–278.
- Krause, J., Winfield, A.F., Deneubourg, J.-L., 2011. Interactive robots in experimental biology. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 26, 369–375.
- Kunz Cechinel, A., Soares, C.E., Pfeleger, S.G., De Oliveira, L.L.G.A., Américo de Andrade, E., Damo Bertoli, C., De Rolt, C.R., De Pieri, E.R., Plentz, P.D.M., Röning, J., 2024. Mobile Robot+ IoT: Project of Sustainable Technology for Sanitizing Broiler Poultry Litter. *Sensors* 24 (10), 3049.
- Lai, J., Wendi, W., Xiaojing, H., Hui, W., Juan, T., Lihua, L., 2023. Design and experiment of dead chicken recognition robot system. *J. Chinese Agric. Mechanization* 44 (8), 81.
- Laschi, C., Mazzolai, B., Cianchetti, M., 2016. Soft robotics: Technologies and systems pushing the boundaries of robot abilities. *Sci. Robotics* 1 (1), p.eaah3690.
- Lei, T., Li, G., Luo, C., Zhang, L., Liu, L., Gates, R.S., 2022. An informative planning-based multi-layer robot navigation system as applied in a poultry barn. *Intelligence & Robotics* 2 (4), 313–332.
- Leinonen, I., Kyriazakis, I., 2016. How can we improve the environmental sustainability of poultry production? *Proc. Nutr. Soc.* 75, 265–273.
- Lemaire, B.S., Vallortigara, G., 2023. Life is in motion (through a chick’s eye). *Animal Cognition* 26 (1), 129–140.
- Li, G., Xu, Y., Zhao, Y., Du, Q., Huang, Y., 2020a. Evaluating convolutional neural networks for cage-free floor egg detection. *Sensors* 20, 332.
- Li, G., Chesser, G.D., Huang, Y., Zhao, Y., Purswell, J.L., 2021. Development and optimization of a deep-learning-based egg-collecting robot. *Trans. ASABE* 64, 1659–1669.
- Li, G., Chesser, G.D., Purswell, J.L., Magee, C., Gates, R.S., Xiong, Y., 2022a. Design and Development of a Broiler Mortality Removal Robot. *Appl. Eng. Agric.* 38, 853–863.
- Li, G., Hui, X., Zhao, Y., Zhai, W., Purswell, J.L., Porter, Z., Poudel, S., Jia, L., Zhang, B., Chesser, G.D., 2022b. Effects of ground robot manipulation on hen floor egg reduction, production performance, stress response, bone quality, and behavior. *PLoS One* 17, e0267568.
- Li, N., Ren, Z., Li, D., Zeng, L., 2020b. Automated techniques for monitoring the behaviour and welfare of broilers and laying hens: towards the goal of precision livestock farming. *Animal* 14, 617–625.
- Li, P., 2016. Study on caged layer health behavior monitoring robot system. (Doctoral dissertation). China Agricultural university, Beijing. Available from CNKI (in Chinese with English abstract).
- Liu, H.-W., Chen, C.-H., Tsai, Y.-C., Hsieh, K.-W., Lin, H.-T., 2021. Identifying images of dead chickens with a chicken removal system integrated with a deep learning algorithm. *Sensors* 21, 3579.
- Liu, Y.C., Li, Y., Li, W.J., Zhou, Y., Cai, L., Li, G.H., Zuo, X.G., 2016. Henhouse Environmental Monitoring System Based on Robot. *J. Acta Ecol. Anim. Domastici* 37, 41–47.
- Mamun, A., 2019. Technological Development in Poultry Business: Comparative Analysis between Bangladesh and Finland. [Master’s Thesis, Centria University of Applied Sciences] <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi:amk-2019092019130>.
- Mandil, W., Rajendran, V., Nazari, K., Ghalamzan-Esfahani, A., 2023. Tactile-sensing technologies: trends, challenges and outlook in agri-food manipulation. *Sensors* 23 (17), 7362.
- Marin, R.H., Caliva, J.M., Kembro, J.M., 2024. Dynamics of changes in broiler spatial distribution induced by a robot with autonomous navigation along the growing cycle. *Poultry Science* 103 (6), 103710.
- McCabe, B.J., 2013. Imprinting. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Cogn. Sci.* 4, 375–390.
- Mellor, D., 14 March 2016. Updating Animal Welfare Thinking: Moving beyond the “Five Freedoms” towards “A Life Worth Living”. *Animals* 6 (3), 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani6030021>.
- Mench, J., 1998. Why it is important to understand animal behavior. *ILAR J.* 39, 20–26.
- Meuser, V., Weinhold, L., Hillemecher, S., Tiemann, I., 2021. Welfare-related behaviors in chickens: characterization of fear and exploration in local and commercial chicken strains. *Animals* 11, 679.
- Miao, Z.H., Glatz, P.C., Ru, Y.J., 2005. Free-range poultry production - a review. *Asian-Australasian J. Animal Sci.* 18 (1), 113–132.
- Mikoni, N.A., Guzman, D.-S.-M., Paul-Murphy, J., 2023. Pain Recognition and Assessment in Birds. *Vet. Clin. Exot. Anim. Pract.* 26, 65–81.
- Mondada, F., Martinoli, A., Correll, N., Gribovskiy, A., Halloy, J.J., Siegwart, R., Deneubourg, J.-L., 2013. A general methodology for the control of mixed natural-artificial societies. *Pan Stanford Publishing Singapore*. Chapter 15, pp. 1–33.
- Mostafavi, S., Ray, D., Warde-Farley, D., Grouios, C., Morris, Q., 2010. A Bayesian framework for combining heterogeneous data sources for gene function prediction. *PLOS ONE* 5 (8), e114487.
- Mottet, A., Tempio, G., 2017. Global poultry production: current state and future outlook and challenges. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 73, 245–256. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0043933917000071>.
- Nicol, C.J., 2015. The behavioural biology of chickens. *CABI*.
- Nicol, C.J., 2019. Feather pecking in laying hens: why they do it, and welfare implications. *Poult. Feathers Skin Poult. Integument Health Welf., Poultry Science Symposium Series* 31–46. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781786395115.0031>.
- Nicol, C., 2020. Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens. *Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing Limited*.
- Nicol, C., 2023. The Gordon Memorial Lecture: Laying Hen Welfare. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 64 (4), 441–447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2023.2211891>.
- Ochs, D., Wolf, C.A., Widmar, N.O., Bir, C., Lai, J., 2019. Hen housing system information effects on US egg demand. *Food Policy* 87, 101743.
- Octopus XO, 2021. XO robot for responsible poultry farming - Octopus Biosafety, <https://www.octopusbiosafety.com/en/xo/> (accessed 26 February 2023).
- Olczak, K., Penar, W., Nowicki, J., Magiera, A., Kłoczek, C., 2023. The role of sound in livestock farming—selected aspects. *Animals* 13, 2307.
- Olejnik, K., Popiela, E., Opaliński, S., 2022. Emerging precision management methods in poultry sector. *Agriculture* 12, 718.
- Oliveira, J.L., Xin, H., Chai, L., Millman, S.T., 2019. Effects of litter floor access and inclusion of experienced hens in aviary housing on floor eggs, litter condition, air quality, and hen welfare. *Poult. Sci.* 98, 1664–1677.

- Olsson, I.A.S., Nicol, J.C., Niemi, S.M., Sandøe, P., 2019. From unpleasant to unbearable—Why and how to implement an upper limit to pain and other forms of suffering in research with animals. *ILAR J.* 60, 404–414.
- Özentürk, U., Yildiz, A., Genc, M., 2022. Assessment of the feather score and health score in laying hens reared at different cage densities. *Ankara Üniversitesi Veteriner Fakültesi Dergisi* 1–22.
- Parajuli, P., Huang, Y., Zhao, Y., Tabler, T., Purswell, J.L., 2018. Comparative evaluation of poultry avoidance distances to human vs. robotic vehicle. In: In: 10th International Livestock Environment Symposium (ILES x). American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers, p. 1.
- Parajuli, P., Huang, Y., Tabler, T., Purswell, J.L., DuBien, J.L., Zhao, Y., 2020. Comparative evaluation of poultry-human and poultry-robot avoidance distances. *Trans. ASABE* 63, 477–484.
- Park, M., Britton, D., Daley, W., McMurray, G., Navaei, M., Samoylov, A., Usher, C., Xu, J., 2022. Artificial intelligence, sensors, robots, and transportation systems drive an innovative future for poultry broiler and breeder management. *Anim. Front.* 12, 40–48.
- Poultry Patrol, 2019, https://poultrypatrol.com/?page_id=472 (accessed 26 February 2023).
- Paul, E.S., Browne, W., Mendl, M.T., Caplen, G., Trevarthen, A., Held, S., Nicol, C.J., 2022. Assessing animal welfare: a triangulation of preference, judgement bias and other candidate welfare indicators. *Anim. Behav.* 186, 151–177.
- Pearce, J., Chang, Y.-M., Abeyesinghe, S., 2023. Individual monitoring of activity and lameness in conventional and slower-growing breeds of broiler chickens using accelerometers. *Animals* 13, 1432.
- Penz, A.M.J., Bruno, D.G., 2011. Challenges Facing the Global Poultry Industry to 2020. *Provimi Am. Lat. Braz. Present. This Years Aust. Poultry Sci. Symp.*
- Petek, M., Çavuşoğlu, E., 2021. Welfare assessment of two free-range laying Hen Flocks in Turkey. *J. Appl. Anim. Welfare Sci.* 24 (1), 56–63.
- Poultry Matic Kft., PoultryMate automatic bedding robot - © 2023 PoultryMatic, <https://poultrymatic.hu/en/home/>. (accessed 11 July 2024).
- Putyora, E., Brocklehurst, S., Tuytens, F., Sandilands, V., 2023. The effects of mild disturbances on sleep behaviour in laying hens. *Animals* 13, 1251.
- Redmon, J., Divvala, S., Girshick, R., Farhadi, A., 2016. You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 779–788.
- Ren, G., Lin, T., Ying, Y., Chowdhary, G., Ting, K.C., 2020. Agricultural robotics research applicable to poultry production: a review. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 169, 105216 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2020.105216>.
- Ribeiro, P., Khan, M.A., Alfaridh, A., Kosel, J., Franco, F., Cardoso, S., Bernardino, A., Schmitz, A., Santos-Victor, J., Jamone, L., 2017. Bioinspired ciliary force sensor for robotic platforms. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Lett.* 2 (2), 971–976.
- Ribeiro, P., Cardoso, S., Bernardino, A., Jamone, L., 2020. October. Fruit quality control by surface analysis using a bio-inspired soft tactile sensor. In: *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pp. 8875–8881.
- Roden, C., Wechsler, B., 1998. A comparison of the behaviour of domestic chicks reared with or without a hen in enriched pens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 55, 317–326.
- Rodić, V., Perić, L., Djukić-Stojičić, M., Vukelić, N., 2011. The environmental impact of poultry production. *Biotechnol. Anim. Husband.* 27, 1673–1679.
- Romano, D., Donati, E., Benelli, G., Stefanini, C., 2019. A review on animal–robot interaction: from bio-hybrid organisms to mixed societies. *Biol. Cybern.* 113, 201–225.
- Rosa-Salva, O., Regolin, L., Vallortigara, G., 2010. Faces are special for newly hatched chicks: evidence for inborn domain-specific mechanisms underlying spontaneous preferences for face-like stimuli. *Develop. Sci.* 13 (4), 565–577.
- Rosa-Salva, O., Fiser, J., Versace, E., Dolci, C., Chehaimi, S., Santolin, C., Vallortigara, G., 2018. Spontaneous learning of visual structures in domestic chicks. *Animals* 8 (8), 135.
- Rosa-Salva, O., Mayer, U., Versace, E., Hébert, M., Lemaire, B.S., Vallortigara, G., 2021. Sensitive periods for social development: interactions between predisposed and learned mechanisms. *Cognition* 213, 104552.
- Sahan, U., Ipek, A., Dikmen, B.Y., 2006. The welfare of egg layer, broiler and turkey, in: *EPC 2006-12th European Poultry Conference*, Verona, Italy, 10-14 September, 2006. *World's Poultry Science Association (WPSA)*.
- Sahoo, P.K., Kushwaha, D.K., Pradhan, N.C., Makwana, Y., Kumar, M., Jatoliya, M., Naik, M.A., Mani, I., 2022. Robotics application in agriculture. In: *55 Annual Convention of Indian Society of Agricultural Engineers and International Symposium*, pp. 60–76.
- Sakamoto, K.S., Benincasa, N.C., Silva, I.J.O., Lobos, C.M.V., 2020. The challenges of animal welfare in modern Brazilian poultry farming. *J. Anim. Behav. Biometeorol.* 8, 131–135.
- Sarica, M., Türkoğlu, M., Yamak, U.S., 2018. Tavukçuluktaki gelişmeler ve Türkiye tavukçuluğu. *Tavukçuluk Bilimi Yetiştirme Besleme Hastalık. Ed. M Türkoğlu M Sarica* 1 (36), 5.
- Scout, 2023. <https://www.scoutmonitoring.com/> (accessed 26 February 2023).
- Sensyn Robotics, Inc., Sensyn robotics and Taiho Industrial Corporation © 2023 Sensyn robotics, <https://www.sensyn-robotics.com/en/news/taiho> (accessed 16 July 2023).
- Sharma, M., Patil, C., 2018. Recent trends and advancements in agricultural research: an overview. *J. Pharmacogn. Phytochem.* 7, 1906–1910.
- Siegford, J.M., Steibel, J.P., Han, J., Benjamin, M., Brown-Brandl, T., Dóra, J.R., Morris, D., Norton, T., Psota, E., Rosa, G.J., 2023. The quest to develop automated systems for monitoring animal behavior. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 265, 106000.
- Slonina, Z., Bonzini, A.A., Brown, J., Wang, S., Farkhatdinov, I., Althoefer, K., Jamone, L., Versace, E., 2021. Using robochick to identify the behavioral features promoting social interactions. In: *2021 IEEE International Conference on Development and Learning (ICDL)*. IEEE, pp. 1–6.
- Tibot, 2021. Le robot avicole Spoutnic NAV, <https://www.tibot.fr/en/rearing/broiler-robot/> (accessed 26 February 2023).
- T-Moov, 2022. The poultry robot T-Moov, <https://www.octopusbiosafety.com/en/t-moov-en/> (accessed 26 July 2023).
- Tomo, T.P., Schmitz, A., Wong, W.K., Kristanto, H., Somlor, S., Hwang, J., Jamone, L., Sugano, S., 2017. Covering a robot fingertip with uSkin: a soft electronic skin with distributed 3-axis force sensitive elements for robot hands. *IEEE Robotics Automation Lett.* 3 (1), 124–131.
- Usher, C.T., Daley, W.D., Joffe, B.P., Muni, A., 2017. Robotics for poultry house management. In: *2017 ASABE Annual International Meeting*. American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers, p. 1. [DOI: 10.13031/AIM.201701103](https://doi.org/10.13031/AIM.201701103).
- Vaarst, M., Steinfeldt, S., Horsted, K., 2015. Sustainable development perspectives of poultry production. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 71, 609–620.
- Vallortigara, G., Versace, E., 2022. Filial Imprinting, in: Vonk, J., Shackelford, T.K. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Animal Cognition and Behavior*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 2726–2728. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55065-7_1989.
- Versace, E., Martinho-Truswell, A., Kacelnik, A., Vallortigara, G., 2018. Priors in animal and artificial intelligence: Where does learning begin? *Trends Cogn. Sci.* 22, 963–965.
- Versace, E., Ragusa, M., Vallortigara, G., 2019. A transient time window for early predispositions in newborn chicks. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 18767.
- Versace, E., Ragusa, M., Pallanu, V., Wang, S., 2021. Attraction for familiar conspecifics in young chicks (*Gallus gallus*): an interbreed study. *Behav. Processes* 193, 104498.
- Vries, M.de, de Boer, I.J.M., 2010. Comparing environmental impacts for livestock products: a review of life cycle assessments. *Livest. Sci.* 128, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2009.11.007>.
- Vroegindewij, B. A., Boots, N.M., Bokkers, E.A.M., 2014a. Chickens don't care about robots: The behaviour of hens towards a mobile robot. In: *WIAS Science Day 2014*.
- Vroegindewij, B.A., Kortlever, J.W., Wais, E., van Henten, E.J., 2014b. Development and test of an egg collecting device for floor eggs in loose housing systems for laying hens. In: *Proceedings International Conference of Agricultural Engineering*, pp. 1–8.
- Vroegindewij, B.A., van Willigenburg, G.L., Koerkamp, P.W.G., van Henten, E.J., 2014c. Path planning for the autonomous collection of eggs on floors. *Biosystems Engineering* 121, 186–199.
- Vroegindewij, B.A., IJsselmuiden, J., van Henten, E.J., 2016. Probabilistic localisation in repetitive environments: estimating a robot's position in an aviary poultry house. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 124, 303–317.
- Vroegindewij, B.A., Blaauw, S.K., IJsselmuiden, J.M., van Henten, E.J., 2018. Evaluation of the performance of PoultryBot, an autonomous mobile robotic platform for poultry houses. *Biosyst. Eng.* 174, 295–315.
- Wang, S., Vasas, V., Freeland, L., Osorio, D., Versace, E., 2024. Spontaneous biases enhance generalization in the neonate brain. *iScience* 27 (7), 110195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.110195>.
- Wang, C.H., Xie, B.X., Chang, C.L., 2019. In: *Design and Implementation of Livestock Robot for Egg Picking and Classification in the Farm*. IEEE, pp. 161–165.
- Webster, J., 2005. *Animal Welfare: Limping Towards Eden*; Wiley-Blackwell: Chichester, UK, 2005.
- Wemelsfelder, F., Mullan, S., 2014. Applying ethological and health indicators to practical animal welfare assessment. *OIE Sci. Tech. Rev.* 33, 111–120.
- Widowski, T.M., Rentsch, A.K., 2022. *Farming poultry*. Routledge Handb. Anim. Welf. 47–63.
- Wilcox, C.H., Sandilands, V., Mayasari, N., Asmara, I.Y., Anang, A., 2023. A literature review of broiler chicken welfare, husbandry, and assessment. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 1–30.
- Wolfert, S., Ge, L., Verdouw, C., Bogaardt, M.-J., 2017. Big data in smart farming—a review. *Agric. Syst.* 153, 69–80.
- Wood, S.M., Wood, J.N., 2015. A chicken model for studying the emergence of invariant object recognition. *Front. Neural Circuits* 9, 7.
- Wu, D., Cui, D., Zhou, M., Ying, Y., 2022. Information perception in modern poultry farming: a review. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 199, 107131.
- Yang, D., Cui, D., Ying, Y., 2024. Development and trends of chicken farming robots in chicken farming tasks: a review. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 221, 108916.
- Yang, X., Huo, X., Li, G., Purswell, J.L., Tabler, G.T., Chesser, G.D., Magee, C.L., Zhao, Y., 2020. Effects of elevated platform and robotic vehicle on broiler production, welfare, and housing environment. *Trans. ASABE* 63, 1981–1990.
- Zenha, R., Denoun, B., Coppola, C., Jamone, L., 2021. Tactile slip detection in the wild leveraging distributed sensing of both normal and shear forces. In: *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pp. 2708–2713.
- Zhang, Y., Chen, Q., Liu, G., Shen, W., Wang, G., 2016. Environment parameters control based on wireless sensor network in livestock buildings. *Int. J. Distrib. Sens. Netw.* 12, 9079748.
- Zhao, Y., 2021. In: *Current Status and Industrialization Development of Industrial Robot Technology*. Springer, Cham, pp. 804–808. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79197-1_117.
- Zhou, Z., Mei, H., Li, R., Wang, C., Fang, K., Wang, W., Tang, Y., Dai, Z., 2022. Progresses of animal robots: a historical review and perspectiveness. *Heliyon* e11499.
- Zuidhof, M.J., Schneider, B.L., Carney, V.L., Korver, D.R., Robinson, F.E., 2014. Growth efficiency, and yield of commercial broilers from 1957, 1978, and 2005. *Poult. Sci.* 93, 2970–2982.